

D8.1 | ENPOWER visual identity and website

NTUA

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Energy Activated Citizens and Data-Driven Energy-Secure Communities for a Consumer-Centric Energy System

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Preface

ENPOWER will design, develop, and demonstrate SSH-driven methodologies, interactive and closed-loop tools, and data-driven services for energy-activated citizens and energy-secure cross-sector communities towards a citizen-centric energy system. We combine leading-edge ICTs with social/behavioural dimensions and with sharing economy and value stacking business models to deploy: 1) a Social Science Framework for energy citizens activation and innovative multidimensional incentives for citizens' participation in energy markets; 2) AI-based consumers clustering and segmentation algorithms; 3) interactive tools and facilitation services for energy community planning; 4) Energy Data Space adaptation to support community-level data-driven activation and interoperable automated privacy and sovereignty-preserving Demand Response (DR); 5) P2P DLT/Blockchain digital marketplace for tokenized energy and non-energy assets reciprocal compensation; 6) data-driven services and apps for energy efficiency and activation performance management; 7) ICT services and Digital Twins for community-level energy optimization and aggregated flexibility management to trade off local self-consumption against grid service provisioning, while boosting a beyond-energy community social welfare; 8) Edge monitoring hubs for automated DR; 9) Business Sandbox for novel sharing economy and social innovation-based business models; 10) methodologies for evaluating different energy community setups, upscaling and replication. ENPOWER framework will be validated along 4 Front Runners energy communities pilots and further replicated in 2 Early Adopters, covering different levels of maturity of communities, to demonstrate increased RES local self-consumption and consumers participation to the energy markets, while nurturing increased local security of supply. ENPOWER Leadership Programme and blueprints will support EU-wide replication and advice regulatory bodies on communities-friendly enabling frameworks.

Who we are.

No	Participant Name	Short Name	Country	Role
1	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	GR	Coordinator
2	Design Strategy Technology S.r.l	Dst	IT	Technology providers
3	INESC TEC - Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science	INESC TEC	PT	
4	Fundación CARTIF (CARTIF Technology Center)	CARTIF	ES	
5	COMSENSUS D.O.O.	COMS	SL	
6	European Dynamics Luxembourg SA	ED	LU	
7	Audencia Business School	AUDENCIA	FR	Business modelling
8	Regulatory Assistance Project	RAP	BE	Regulatory assistance
9	ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH	ICLEI	DE	Policy & capacity
10	University of Basel(<i>associated partner</i>)	UNIBAS	CH	Social framework
11	Blueprint Energy Solutions GMBH	BLUEPRINT	AT	Pilot 1 - Austria (Front runners)
12	OurPower Energiegenossenschaft SCE	OurPower	AT	
13	Cooperativa de Desenvolvimento Sustentável, CRL	COOPERNICO	PT	Pilot 2 - Portugal (Front runners)
14	WATT-IS SA	WATT-IS	PT	
15	Cooperativa Eléctrica do Vale D'Este CRL	CEVE	PT	
16	Energy Community of Chalki'Chalkion'	ChalkiON	GR	Pilot 3 - Greece (Front runners)
17	Hellenic Association for Energy Economics	HAEE	GR	
18	Green Energy Aggregator Services SA	GEARS	GR	
19	Parity Platform P.C.	PARITY	GR	

20	Electric Power Research Institute Europe DAC	EEU	IE	Pilot 4 - Ireland (Front runners)
21	University College Cork (MaREI Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine, Environmental Research Institute)	UCC	IE	
22	DC Six Technologies Limited	DCSix	IE	
23	MOL TEIC - Dingle Hub	DINGLE HUB	IE	
24	ESB Innovation ROI Limited	ESB	IE	
25	Békéscsaba Energia ESCO Kft.	BCS	HU	Pilot 5 - Hungary (Early adopters)
26	Enasco Cleantech Alliance LLC.	ENASCO	HU	
27	Montajes Eléctricos Cuerva SL	CUERVA	ES	Pilot 6 - Spain (Early adopters)
28	VERGY COMMUNITY S.L. (<i>affiliated partner</i>)	VER	ES	

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	9
2. VISUAL IDENTITY	9
2.1 THE ENPOWER LOGO	9
3. ENPOWER PROJECT PRESENTATION.....	11
4. PROMOTIONAL AND INFORMATIONAL MATERIAL	11
4.1 ENPOWER FLYER	12
4.2 ENPOWER LEAFLET.....	13
4.3 ENPOWER POSTER	15
4.4 ENPOWER ROLL UP	15
4.5 ENPOWER E-NEWSLETTER	16
5. ENPOWER WEBSITE.....	17
5.1 DESIGN	17
5.2 STRUCTURE AND CONTENT	18
DATA PROTECTION COMPLIANCE FOR THE WEBSITE.....	19
NEXT STEPS.....	20
ANNEX	21

Figures

<i>Figure 1: The ENPOWER logo</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Figure 2: ENPOWER main branding colours.....</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Figure 3: The ENPOWER presentation</i>	<i>11</i>
<i>Figure 4: ENPOWER Flyer</i>	<i>13</i>
<i>Figure 5: ENPOWER Leaflet (front view).....</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Figure 6: ENPOWER Leaflet (back view)</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Figure 7: ENPOWER Poster</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Figure 8: ENPOWER Roll Up.....</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>Figure 9: ENPOWER website</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>Figure 10: Website's menu</i>	<i>19</i>

List of acronyms

EC	European Commission
DCS	Dissemination and Communication Secretariat
ToC	Table of Contents
WPL	Work Package Leader
WP	Work Package
TL	Task Leader

1. Introduction

The goal of this document is to summarise the visual identity and online presence of the ENPOWER project. It is a lively document developed in Month 4 of the project's life i.e., December and will be updated in months 18 and 36 in D8.3.

In the following sections, the key elements of the visual identity will be displayed and explained while the mock-up of the website landing page, the specs, and the site map will be provided. An outline of the project flyer, leaflet, and roll-up banner will also be included. The document outlines the guidelines on the identity of the project in all its online presence, including the word and ppt templates, the project colours, fonts, etc.

The document is structured as follows. Initially it provides all the necessary information on the visual identity and the key messages of the project's communication. Following, the document includes detailed information on the structure of the website and how its content is going to be demonstrated, as well as a detailed description of the Social Media presence of the project. In addition, the document presents a description of the promotional material, i.e., the flyer, leaflet, poster, roll-up banner, and presentation that are planned to be used throughout its duration.

A broader communication and dissemination strategy for the project, along with details on the goals of it, are complementary to the deliverable at hand and presented in detail in Deliverable 8.2, titled "D8.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan".

2. Visual Identity

External communication aims mainly to broadcast the project's messages and results and to draw the interest and attention of interested stakeholders. The language that is to be used has to be rather easy to understand and avoid more specific technical jargon, referring to general concepts or images to explain more complex ideas. To this end, the visual language to be used will prioritise to convey key messages with visual attractiveness.

Making use of the agreed ENPOWER messages and the external communication tools described below will be of key importance to achieve content alignment, reach the broader public and facilitate the project's replication across borders.

2.1 The ENPOWER Logo

ENPOWER aims at transforming the energy system in a consumer centric structure by activating and engaging citizens and providing data driven tools and services for energy secure communities. A simple, clear but characteristic and attractive visual identity is essential, so the logo, as one of the integral parts of the project's visual identity, encapsulates the project's dynamic and innovative spirit by embracing the notions of community, clean energy and overall sustainability. As described in D8.2 the ENPOWER logo is complemented with the tagline. The "tagline" is a memorable and explanatory sentence accompanying the project's title. Taglines capture the essence and meaning of the project and often suggest a call for action or a statement. ENPOWER has been more closely connected with the tagline - "Power in our hands" - and partners are welcome to use it to explain the goal of the project in just a couple of words.

Figure 1: The ENPOWER logo

Clear space is defined as the area around the logo that is free of other elements (including page or other surface edges). A clear space of 1/3 of the logo's height is recommended.

When resizing the ENPOWER logo, the structure, and proportions (the relationship between the emblem, the logotype and the logo title) must always remain intact and must never be altered. The stipulated proportions are intended to preserve legibility as well as proper visibility from distance.

The main colors of the project – green, blue, and yellow - need to be coherently used across all types of publications.

Figure 2: ENPOWER main branding colours

3. ENPOWER Project Presentation

The Project presentation can be used for dissemination purposes by all partners. It contains all the important information about the project, the objectives, methodology employed, key expected results, and expected impact. More specifically, the presentation includes the consortium, the objectives, the target groups, the innovative framework, the expected results, as well as the social media channels and the contact information. It will be used by the partners as the main presentation tool, for dissemination purposes at relevant events.

The presentation will be regularly updated, and it can be modified by the partners according to their specific needs of the target audience they address (the main project elements and EU funding will be displayed on any occasion).

The digital version of the ENPOWER Presentation will be available for download on the website as well. The presentation's cover page is shown in the figure below and the full content can be found in the Annex in detail.

Figure 3: The ENPOWER presentation

4. Promotional and Informational material

The dissemination activities will bring the message of ENPOWER to a broad and diverse audience with special focus on people and stakeholders active in the energy sector, in local and regional administration, in energy communities and so on. To successfully achieve that, a flexible and mixed strategy will be followed.

The ENPOWER project will need to communicate its objectives and results in digital environments, and ideally, in person as well. For this reason, a number of digital and printed materials will be

prepared and handed out to partners to multiply their distribution. They will also be added to the ENPOWER website and shared via the project's social media accounts.

Partners will be asked to report where, how and when the promotional materials have been distributed. A specialized form for that is shared in the section regarding 'monitoring and impact'.

Such materials may indicatively and not exclusively be the following:

- The Flyer that is in A5 and contains key information about the project, and the website and social media channels to connect.
- The leaflet shall be threefold A4 or slightly larger when printed, the digital version will be available on the website of the project. It will be distributed to key actors, target groups and interested parties at events, seminars, workshops. The leaflet contains more information about the project, including the objectives, the key expected results, and the expected impact.
- A poster, containing information about the project, it will be in A3 and available on the website.
- Roll-up poster explaining the ENPOWER concept and objectives, key results and expected impact. This will be 2 meters high and 0.8 meters wide. This is ideal for large events. It will also be available on the website.
- E-newsletter for the dissemination of project's results to be distributed by e-mail regularly (about once every 6 months).
- The project presentation will be used as a common reference point and be available for the partners to customise and use in events when presenting the project.

All the promotional and informational materials can be translated in the local languages to further enable the local partners to communicate with local stakeholders.

4.1 ENPOWER flyer

The flyer has been prepared for the project's dissemination in a wide audience, it has basic information about the concept of the project and links to the website, and social media channels. The aim of the flyer is to nudge stakeholders to look into the project with a short inviting message. The outline of the flyer is presented below.

Figure 4: ENPOWER Flyer

4.2 ENPOWER Leaflet

A leaflet has been prepared for the project’s dissemination to all target audiences and interested parties. The promotional leaflet will be distributed among general public, key stakeholders, policy and decision makers, academic researchers etc.

The leaflet briefly outlines the aim, the leading objectives, the key expected results, and the expected impact, the Consortium synthesis of the project, the social media channels, and contact information. The idea behind the brochure’s design is to create a square twofold brochure in A4 size which consists of six distinctive sections. It is simple, easy to hold and read.

According to project’s requirements, the brochure has initially been produced in English, and will be available both electronically and in hard copy. Moreover, it can be translated into the pilot countries’ languages to have the best possible communication and dissemination results and increase the outreach. The digital version of the ENPOWER brochure will be available for download on the website. The ENPOWER leaflet is presented below.

Figure 5: ENPOWER Leaflet (front view)

Figure 6: ENPOWER Leaflet (back view)

4.3 ENPOWER Poster

A project’s poster has been created to be used at events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. The Poster has been produced in A5 size and is available in English and it can be translated in the pilot countries’ languages in order to have the best possible communication and dissemination results. The digital version of the Poster will be available to download in ENPOWER’s website. The following Figure shows the Poster in English.

Figure 7: ENPOWER Poster

4.4 ENPOWER Roll Up

The ENPOWER Roll-up has been also designed for events organised by the project partners or hosted by other relevant organisations and will be available in English. The Roll-up Size will be 80 cm X 200 cm, and due to its own retracting mechanism built from aluminium, it is easily portable and setup.

The logo and the concept of the project are displayed on the top while the image, the graphic and textual elements are clear, easy to read and in coherence with the project’s visual identity. It also includes the expected impact, the social media channels, contact Information and the Partners’ Logos. The ENPOWER Roll-up’s digital version will be available to download on the website and is presented below.

Figure 8: ENPOWER Roll Up

4.5 ENPOWER e-Newsletter

For the efficient dissemination of project’s progress, 4 e-newsletters will be developed in English and translated in all project languages and distributed by e-mail to all subscribed stakeholders and interested parties. The first e-Newsletter will be released in March 2024.

This communication channel can contribute greatly to the project's dissemination, in building an online community, in incentivising the subscribers' presence with a strong call-to-action, as well as in guiding them to the website and the social media channels. By delivering valuable content to the project's subscribers inbox, they stay connected and engaged while activity is generated and the traffic on the website and the social media is increased. The ENPOWER e-Newsletters will be also available to download on the website.

5. ENPOWER website

The website will be the reference point when it comes to the online presence of ENPOWER and will be launched January 2024. The web page will aim at informing the visitors about the project objectives, strategy, results, the latest news and the upcoming events.

The domain name of the project has been secured and is <https://enpower-project.eu/>. It contains the name of the project, with the .eu extension denoting its European origin. The selected wording fulfils the primary requirements of a successful domain name: it is short, descriptive and easy to remember.

The website is built upon the latest version of the Drupal operating system, which is a free, open-source content management system (CMS).

For measuring the website traffic and monitoring the visitors' behaviour, a connection with the Google Analytics service has been established and configured. The data insights coming from the ENPOWER website can be accessed directly from the Google Analytics interface.

5.1 Design

The design of the ENPOWER website follows the latest trends in web design, having also in mind the special characteristics of the project's objectives and visual identity.

More specifically, the ENPOWER website exhibits the following properties:

- A modern, clean, and light interface, with contrasting colours for the text and background to make reading easier on the eye and with vibrant colours being only used for emphasis (e.g., links) where necessary.
- Easy navigation to content through a comprehensive structure that is implemented both on the front page and the various menus.
- A clean and modern typography utilised throughout the website and all sections, with large fonts that are easier to read.
- A responsive design, making the website respond and adapt to the user's input and environment, based on their device (desktop/laptop computer, tablet, or mobile/smartphone) and screen size.

Overall, the ENPOWER website is built on modern web design principles, focusing on usability, accessibility, and intuitive navigation.

An initial draft of the homepage has already been created and has been circulated to the partners for feedback. The website will be created by incorporating input from all the partners. The initial draft of the homepage can be found below.

Figure 9: ENPOWER website

The homepage of the website includes a short description of the project, two buttons leading to the project’s social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube), a life feed of the recent news and events with a vertical scrolling function, a live feed of the latest tweets with a horizontal scrolling function, links to the pages of the tools and services, an interactive map with the pilot countries highlighted, leading to each pilot country’s dedicated page, and a stay connected form for users to directly register to our newsletter.

5.2 Structure and content

The site can be navigated by using the main menu links, which are located at the top part of every website page. This is a two-level navigation menu that aims to guide the visitor in a simple and intuitive manner. Currently, it contains the following items:

Figure 10: Website's menu

- **About:** here a description of the project, and of the partners with a direct link to their individual websites will be demonstrated in different sub-tabs.
- **Pilot site:** here an interactive map that has the 6 pilot countries in two different colours (separating the front runners from the early adopters) will be provided.
- **Tools and Services:** icons of the tools and services, i.e., the Citizen Renewable Platform, the Peer-to-Peer online Marketplace, the energy consumption optimisation tool, and a short description for each tool will be demonstrated. Some videos of services may also be included here. By clicking on the icon, the user will be directed at the interface of the corresponding tool. At the end of the page, space should be available on the page for the users to be able to fill in a form to subscribe to the newsletter. Text about GDPR law to be added. EU logo with funding information.
- **News & Events:** here all the relevant news about the project, or news affecting the project, along with all the relevant events and the events that ENPOWER has been disseminated in will be presented.
- **Resources:** here all the deliverables of the project will be listed in the sub-section Results. Also, all the publications that are going to be published with the project results will be included in the sub-section Publications.
- **Communication:** all the channels of communication will be gathered in this page along with the helpdesk that will be developed.

The first draft of the website's homepage has been circulated to the consortium to get their feedback, so that the final website to be developed is cocreated by all the partners.

Data Protection Compliance for the website

The ENPOWER website will have a specific section in which the following legal notices will be displayed:

Terms of use: In this section the information to be displayed are the links to other websites and user-supplied content, privacy, copyright and trademarks, the user submissions and conduct.

Privacy policy: In this section, information on the users' data that are collected when they visit the ENPOWER website and how those are going to be used, will be available.

Cookies policy: General information about cookies (use preference cookies, marketing and preference cookies, third party analytics cookies) will be presented.

GDPR Policy: In this section the overall GDPR policy of the ENPOWER project will be available. The policy will include the following sections: the general data privacy regulation scope, information of the data controller, the purpose and legal basis for data processing, the recipients of personal data, the process and storage of personal data, users' rights, and the users' right to lodge a complaint with the competent data protection authority.

Next steps

The next steps include the translation of the promotional and informational materials to the national languages where it is considered necessary according to the national context. The website will be populated with all the material needed and it will be disseminated through social media. The website will be updated periodically.

Annex

Energy Activated Citizens and Data-Driven Energy-Secure Communities for a Consumer-Centric Energy System

Name of Presenter(s) - Name of Organisation, Country
Date of presentation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101096354

<p>Energy Activated Citizens and Data-Driven Energy-Secure Communities for a Consumer-Centric Energy System ENPOWER</p>	<p>Started: 01/09/2023 Duration: 36 Months</p>	<p>Coordinator: National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Participants: 28</p>
<p>Budget: 5.999.718,75€</p>	<p>Grant Agreement number: 101096354</p>	

Who we are

ENPOWER VISION

The overall vision of ENPOWER is to design, develop and demonstrate SSH-driven methodologies, interactive and closed-loop tools and services for energy activated citizens and data-driven energy-secure communities towards a consumer-centric energy system

ENPOWER strives to:

Social

Connect: Educate citizens to understand energy, current plans and technologies by using SSH tools and methodologies.

Incentivise: Require innovative multi-dimensional incentives that go beyond traditional financial remuneration to overcome the challenge of insufficient incentive and compensation mechanisms, particularly in valuing beyond-financial cross-energy and cross-sector social value.

Technological

Plan: Provide the necessary digital tools and frameworks to take various actions in cross-commodity and cross-sectoral energy communities.

Share: Grow the value and culture of data sharing by reinforcing trust and transparency in the development of the Energy Data Space compliant tools.

Interact & Manage: Activate consumers by ensuring an intuitive and effective real time interaction throughout the tools and exploit additional flexibility mobilisation by leveraging on commodity-agnostic energy management.

Business

Benefit: Share economy and social innovation - based business models.

Integrate: Provide new enabling regulatory and market frameworks for the effective operationalisation of the consumer-centric decentralised energy systems.

Objectives

Social layer

The Social Layer will unlock consumer preferences and behaviour within energy communities, enhancing citizen engagement, rooted in Design Thinking methodologies, fostering dialogue among stakeholders, facilitating a co-creation and co-implementation process for consumer-centred, data-driven services and incentives.

Technological layer

The Technological Layer encompasses a suite of services and tools for individual and community-level energy activation including an the Energy Community Planning Tool that provides energy activated citizens with an intuitive view of their energy activation effects, promoting informed choices and community-level benefits.

Business layer

The Business Layer innovates the energy sector dynamics through the design and validation of novel collective aggregation archetypes, like cross-commodity and cross-sector energy communities. This expansion includes the introduction of an Energy Data Community, potentially overseeing a Data Space-driven marketplace.

Target Groups

Pilots

Key Results

Expected Impact

Economic

- 13-15% cost reduction in the energy bill for activated energy consumers
- 15% increased energy efficiency

Technological

- Harmonise and extend existing automation-oriented standards, business DR standards, ontologies, and languages
- 45% increased energy data sharing by active consumers after 5 years
- 10 new data-driven services to facilitate consumer activation and market participation

Societal

- 30-35 energy communities created, set up, and/or upscaled/replicated after five years from the project starting date
- >1500 consumers engaged and >1000 consumers activated
- 40% average yearly increase of the share of consumers energy market participation via energy communities
- > 500 active consumers engaged in automated DR
- 15-20% carbon emission reduction in the areas of the 6 pilots due to increased decentralised management of energy infrastructures

